

English Teachers' Techniques of Teaching Stories for Students: A Study of Secondary Level School in Nepal

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Abstract

This research work was conducted to find out the techniques used by English language teachers in teaching short stories to the secondary school level students in Nepal. To achieve the research objectives, the researcher chosen a case study design. The data were analyzed on the basis of activities recorded during the class observation. In this regard, the researcher used judgmental non-random sampling procedure to select two English language teachers from two secondary schools in Banke district, Nepalgunj, Nepal. Further, 30 classes (15 classes of each teacher) were observed. Diary writing and observation checklists were used to collect data. After analyzing the data, it was found that teachers used student-centered teaching techniques i.e., interaction technique, discussion technique, problem solving technique and question answer technique to teach short stories.

Keywords: English language teachers; story teaching activities; story teaching at Nepali schools; story teaching techniques

1. Introduction

1.1 Background of the Study

Literature is an important and reliable material to teach language. It includes diverse genres like poetry, story, drama, essay and novel. As short stories are important genre of literature, they provide a wide-ranging body of written materials. It has been taught from to advanced levels. At advanced level, stories are taught for critical appreciation where stories are analyzed from narrative point of view. Moreover, stories are explained in terms of cultural background, characterization, by analyzing plot, setting and theme and so on. However, at secondary level, short stories are taught for general purposes i.e., for providing enjoyment, developing reading habit, to enrich vocabulary power, to make them familiar with creative world, to provide moral lesson and so on. In grade 10 English textbook, there are short stories along with pictures for the development of language skills. The tasks are set for guessing answers, finding a suitable title, arranging jumbled sentences in correct order, gap filling and solving very short answer questions and so on.

There are many languages in the world. Among them, English is a language which is widely used all over the world as a means of communication. In the context of our country, English has been given more priority to other international languages such as Chinese, French and German. In recent years, it is taught as a compulsory subject (from grade one to bachelor degree programs) as a foreign language (EFL) in Nepal. The introduction of ELT in Nepal was started only in 1971 with the implementation of National Education System Plan 1971. There are a number of ways through which stories can be presented in the classroom. Some teachers are still adopting traditional techniques and some teachers are trying to follow communicative way but they are not much successful to handle the problems in the classroom. The very divergent situation can be found. This is due to the different factors such as lack of training and skills, problems with physical environment, overcrowded classroom, lack of interest/motive of the teacher and so on.

It is clear that there is not found any clear-cut format to teach short stories. But generally, stories can be taught through following three stages (Lazar, 1993, p. 83):

- 1) Pre-reading activities
- 2) While-reading activities
- 3) Post-reading activities

Though, theoretically the techniques of teaching short stories are separated in the three stages. The existing situation of teaching stories may not reflect the same. In this scenario, the present study seeks to analyze the techniques adopted by the teachers in teaching short stories at secondary level in English classroom.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Teaching is a complex task. While teaching in the classroom, different teachers use different techniques which are not appropriate according to the context. That could not address the students' needs. To make it effective and appropriate, the language teacher should adopt innovative techniques while teaching a short story in the classroom. Teaching techniques are used to facilitate learners for target language and provide them better learning. In case of teaching short stories, the teachers use the traditional teacher-centered techniques. They might not have started to teach according to the learners' interest and their ability of learning. Therefore, it is necessary to study what kinds of techniques are used in teaching stories in the classroom.

1.3 Objectives of the Study

The study had the following objectives:

- To find out the techniques of teaching short stories at secondary level; and
- To suggest some pedagogical implications based on findings.

1.4 Delimitations of the Study

The scope of this study was limited on the following points:

- This study was limited to the secondary school level education of Nepal. This study was limited to identify short story teaching techniques only;
- In addition, this study was limited to two English language teachers. This study was conducted only in Banke district, Nepalgunj, Nepal.

2. Review of Related Literature

2.1 Review of Theoretical Literature

As theoretical literature review, this researcher has presented different concepts and theories related to the topic. This review of theoretical literature consists of techniques of teaching short stories to secondary level students. It is needed to understand the introduction of short stories, element of short stories, types of short stories, importance of short stories and techniques of teaching short stories. These are the material of teaching not only in Nepal, but also in many countries and cultures.

2.1.1 Short Story

A story is a creatively knitted plot which focuses on the past events in an order of events. A short story has a very few characters, a single setting and a single incident. Abrams (2001. P. 193) defines short story as, "a brief work of prose fiction and its most of the terms for analyzing the component elements, the types and the various narrative techniques of the novel are applicable to the short story as well". Short stories, in fact, are those stories that can be read easily in a single setting. The elements of short stories are; plot, character, dialogue, setting, language style, and theme.

2.1.2 Use of Short Story for Language Teaching

Collie and Slater (1987, p. 109) posits that short stories are the ideal ways of introducing students to literature in the foreign language classroom because of the following points:

- a) Short stories can usually be dealt with in a single class;
- b) They are less difficult for foreign learners to understand;
- c) Teacher can choose varieties of short stories according to their tastes and student interests; and
- d) Short stories can be used for long term and also for short term courses.

2.1.3 Short Stories Teaching techniques

Commonly used short story teaching techniques are introduced by McWilliams (1995).

1) Narration

Narration is the way to narrate or tell the events. The other ways of presenting a story are:

- a) Make the students to read the story which they like to;
- b) Make students to involve into role play;
- c) Teacher and students may also share their own experiences as a story; and
- d) They involve into discussion.

2) Participation

Participation of the students can be taken as follows:

- a) The participation story;
- c) Stories with repetitive elements;
- d) Choral, chant and echo story'
- e) Pantomime;
- f) Acting it out; and
- g) Role playing

3) Visuals Aids

Visual aids become helpful to deal when the story includes unfamiliar elements. Picture can be more informative than words.

- a) Visual aids are effective if the children find the story hard to imagine. Picture is best to show before telling the story to avoid distraction of the students from the story.
- b) Pictures in sequence help exemplify a simple story.
- c) Flannel graph stories are helpful when story sequence, movement and relationships are in the story.
- d) Stories in sequence
- e) Art board stories: The key to these is the element of suspense and surprise.

4) Character Stories

From the role playing, the difficult thoughts of the story can be presented in a simple way to make students easy to understand it.

5) Dramatic

In a story multiple characters have significant roles. Different characters and putting on different personalities make the story clear.

6) Role Playing

Role playing is different from dramatizing the story. In it, children take on various roles.

7) Play Activities

It makes children thinking as they are playing not just reading stories.

8) Puppets

Puppet can be used to get the outcome of the story known to the students.

9) Using Flannel Graph

Flannel graph is a most versatile and effective teaching tool in story teaching.

Lazar (1993) talks about the following tasks and activities for teaching short stories:

A) Pre-Reading Activities

It is the first stage of teaching a short story in the classroom. The teacher makes the students ready for the lesson and the tasks to be performed. Here, the teacher can ask some questions related to the story to draw the attention of the students or s/he can ask them to describe the pictures related to the stories. The following activities can be conducted at this stage:

- To help students with cultural background;
- To stimulate students' interest in the story; and
- To teach them pre-teaching vocabulary.

B) While-Reading Activities

Here, the teacher presents the task to be performed. The students read the story silently and answer the questions. The teacher is required to watch students and evaluate their activities. The following activities are performed at this stage:

- To help students understand the plot and the characters;
- To help students be familiar with difficult vocabulary; and
- To help students be familiar with style and language.

C) Post-Reading Activities

Here, the students' answers are checked by the teacher. The teacher clarifies the ambiguities of the students. The following activities are utilized at this stage:

- To help students make interpretations of the story;
- To understand narrative point of view; and
- To follow-up writing activities and fluency practice.

2.1.5 The Stories Included at Secondary Level (Grade-10)

At secondary level (Grade-10) English course i.e. "Our English Book" consists of six short stories:

- The Story of Zamindar
- The Story of Ms Pradhan
- The Story of Writer
- The Biography of Florence Nightingale
- How a Boy Manages to Persuade His Parents
- A Problematic School Boy

2.2 Review of Empirical Literature

This researcher has studied some of the researches carried out at the Department of English Education, Tribhuvan University regarding teaching. These are related to teaching short stories. Some of the researches reviewed in this section are presented below.

Joshi (2008) conducted a research on "Teaching English Short Stories Interactively". The primary objective of his study was to measure the usefulness of teaching stories interactively at the primary level in term of their performance and the materials used to teach them. After analysing the data, his findings showed that materials prepared by the researcher were good, eye-catching and motivating. Students' interaction flourished after they were taught short stories interactively. Students participated actively in interaction activities but they were not perfectly able to handle the task they were assigned at the beginning phase gradually they could handle it well as they had been exposed to interactive activities in the following texts and helped create the story themselves but it showed that primary students were not competent enough to handle interaction compared to participation.

In the same way, Kshetri (2010) carried out a research study entitled "Activities in Teaching Short Stories". The aim of his study was to find out the activities used in teaching short stories at lower secondary level. His sample size was 40 students and 20 lower secondary level English language teachers from different public and private schools in Dang district. He had used judgmental non-random sampling under non-random sampling procedure.

Regmi (2011) carried out a research entitled "Activities Used in Teaching Literature". The aim of her study was to find out the activities used in teaching poetry and short stories at higher secondary level. Her sample size was 10 teachers of each district. She used purposive sampling under non-random sampling to gather the information. Similarly, her research tool was questionnaire. From the study, it was found that most of the teachers teaching in Kathmandu helped their students understand the plot. On the other hand, only 25% teachers from Jhapa did so. It was found that 40% teachers teaching in Kathmandu used the discussion technique. On the other hand, only few teachers from Jhapa used this technique. It was found that about 70% teachers from Kathmandu gave different types of exercises in the teaching story. On the contrary, 12% of the teachers did so from Jhapa.

After reviewing these works this researcher got lots of ideas regarding the techniques i.e., which is teaching techniques, how they are used in the classroom, what sorts of teaching techniques are used the most at that particular level (in teaching short stories).

3. Methods and Procedures of the Study

The following methodology was adopted to fulfill the aim of this research:

3.1 Design of the Study

Qualitative research design in general is used in this study and the case study design in particular.

3.1.1 Qualitative Research

Qualitative research is a field of naturalistic inquiry of a phenomenon, situation, human nature, etc. to penetrate into the multiple realities. It opposes the normative approach that human behaviour is essentially rule-governed, single and objective reality. The qualitative researcher is believer in the use of multiple methods or triangulation for subjective reality. My study is also qualitative in nature. The researcher (I) attempted to study my cases in a natural setting by repeated measures with non-participant observation. The researcher also tried to make the study evocative, descriptive, interpretive, analytic, and lively by utilizing my own feelings and voices to document and present scenes, sights, smells and individuals as realistically as possible which the researcher brought from a field visit where his cases normally live and work.

3.1.2 Case Study Approach

The main approach of this research study is case study approach. It is not a methodological choice but a choice of what is to be studied as my study is qualitative in nature and case study fits comfortably into the description of case in my study. Merriam (in Nunan, 1992, p. 77) defines the term case study as:

The qualitative case study can be defined as an intensive, holistic description and analysis of a single entity, phenomenon or social limit. Case studies are particularistic, descriptive, and heuristic and rely heavily on inductive reasoning a handling multiple data source.

In order to collect data for in depth information the researcher observed 15 classes of each 2 teacher to identify the techniques of teaching short stories at the secondary level. At the time of observation, the researcher utilized diary writing to find the techniques.

3.2 Population, Sample and Sampling Strategy

English language teachers of secondary level in Banke district were the population of the study. In doing so, two English language teachers were the sample of this study. The researcher used judgmental non-random sampling procedure to select two English teachers of secondary level.

3.3 Study Area

The study area of this research was the academic field of Banke district. The researcher carried out this research work at the secondary level in Banke district, Nepalgunj.

3.4 Data Collection Tools and Techniques

In order to collect data, the researcher used non-participant observation. The researcher used observation checklist and diary writing as recording devices.

3.5 Data Collection Procedure

After preparing the research tools, the researcher visited the purposively selected secondary schools and talked to the authorities to get permission to carry out the research by explaining the purpose and process of research, and then the researcher met the concerned teachers, explained the purpose of the research and requested them to allow to observe their classes for 15 days. The researcher observed the class of teachers while they taught the story and tried to identify the techniques of teaching short stories at secondary level.

3.6 Data Analysis Procedure

The collected data were analyzed descriptively as well as analytically by using charts, tables and diagrams.

4. Result Analysis and Interpretation

The data (collected from the classroom observation and diary notes of classroom interaction) have been used in it. This research tries to find out various types of techniques used by the English teachers of Nepalgunj in teaching short stories for students in secondary classes. The information was tabulated and discussed after direct classroom observation.

4.1 Analysis of Diary Record

To find out the technique of teaching the short stories, the researcher did diary writing while they taught the short stories in the classroom. The activities done by the teachers were analyzed descriptively.

Out of 15 observed classes of teacher '1' five were started through questioning like:

What did we study yesterday?
Which lesson we are going to read today?
Did you read the story of yesterday?

And 3 were started by cracking jokes like: A teacher taught abcd.....

Like this 'a' for father of Amar, 'b' for father of Bala, 'c' for father of Chandra

Then students did not read the 'w' for so they guess for a while and said 'w' for father of Mane, but he is hanging upside down. He used the board to write the topic, unit and page number. He asked signpost questions in most of the classes. For example:

What couldn't the old man remember?
Why did he fight with?

Why was the writer in a dilemma?

He always read the story first and asked to read the story to the students. He always translated the sentence wise meaning of the story in Nepali language. He explained the story in simple English language in all classes. He always asked the meaning of new vocabulary to the student's first like:

What is the meaning of the word 'abandon'?
 Can you say what the meaning of the word 'disaster'?
 Can you tell me what the meaning of the word 'irrigation' is?
 Can you guess what the meaning of the word 'require' is? And, then wrote the meaning on the board like this:
 Abandon- give up
 Disaster-sudden happening of the cause
 Irrigation- supply dry land with water
 Require- demand, need

He always encouraged students to take part in interaction in the classroom like this: Please Sarita you stand up and ask the questions about the lesson Zamindar to Durga. (Sarita stood up and asked questions in this way)

Sita: What couldn't the old man remember?
 Rita: The old man couldn't remember that how many generations of lotuses had bloomed and faded in the pond since he was born.
 Sita: Why did he fight with the Zamindar?
 Rita: Because the son of the landlord (Zamindar) had claimed his land.
 Sita: Who is Rani?
 Rita: A cow.
 Sita: Who lost the legal fight and how?
 Rita: Prodip Pal, because the judge had been bought (bribed).
 Sita: How did the Pals survive when they had no rice left?
 Rita: lived on fruit and vegetables.
 Sita: What did Prodip Pal do to protect his family from the disaster?
 Rita: Mortgaged the land for four hundred pounds of rice.
 Sita: What was the bad sign?
 Rita: The cow angry.

He always asked students the meaning of the new vocabulary at first and encouraged them to tell the meaning and finally he himself wrote it on the board. For example, at the time of teaching the word attack he taught like this: "Can you guess the meaning of the word attack"? "Listen carefully I give one example, 'The North Korea' is ready to attack South Korea. Then tell me, what is the meaning of the word attack in this sentence"? "Attack- to go and fight against something". At the time of teaching stories, he took 70% of the time to talk and 30% of the time was given to the students. At the time of teaching new vocabularies, he gave synonyms and antonyms of those words in 7 classes. For example: while teaching the word 'silence'. He gave the antonyms and synonyms in this way:

The antonym of the word 'silence' is noise.
 The synonym of the word silence is quiet.

Teacher '2' started the class with asking questions about a student in all classes like this:

What did Hari do at school and at home?
 Why couldn't the teacher give Hari her full attention?
 Why did the teacher reprimand and punish Hari?
 What were the reasons for his bad behaviour?
 What was the 'vicious circle' that Hari was caught in?

He used the board to write the unit, page number and topic in all observed classes. He started the class with asking questions on the related topic in all classes like this:

Which topic /lesson we are going to read today?
 Is it a story or poem?

He always used white board to write unit, page number and topic. He asked to guess about story by the help of topic and by reading first paragraph in five classes. He asked the signpost questions in seven classes. For example:

Why did Florence Nightingale go to Germany?
 Name the countries that assisted Turkey in the Crimean war.
 Why was she called the "Lady with the lamp"?
 Why did Florence Nightingale's parents oppose her decision to take up nursing?

At first, he read the story with the sentence wise explanation and translation into the Nepali language and then asked to the students to read the story in all classes. He asked the meaning of the new vocabulary to the students first and encouraged them to tell the meaning and finally he himself told and wrote on the white board the meaning of the new vocabularies in all classes.

For examples: While teaching the word comfortable sank, trained, shrewdly, enjoyed, depressed and inventive. Teacher asked:

Sita, what is the meaning of the word 'comfortable'?
 Hari, tell me a meaning of the word 'sank'?
 Isa, can you tell the meaning of the word 'trained'?
 Niru, what is the meaning of the word 'shrewdly'?
 Raj, what is the meaning of the word 'enjoyed'?
 Kamal, tell me the meaning of the word 'depressed'?
 Neeru, can you tell me the meaning of the word 'inventive'?

And then the teacher asked "who can say the meaning of the all above written word"? "Please! Stand up and say'. After listening the answer from the students, he himself told and wrote the meaning on the white board in this way:

Comfortable: cozy, homely, soothing
 Sank: dropped

Trained: disciplined, drilled
 Shrewdly: knowingly
 Enjoyed: basked, loved, relished
 Depressed: sad, unhappy
 Inventive: able to make up new things for the first time

At the time of teaching stories, he took half of the time to talk and same portion of the time was given to the students. He gave similar examples and illustrations in Nepali and English languages at the time of teaching new vocabularies in all classes.

4.1.2 Analysis of the Teaching Technique Recorded in the Checklist

The researcher observed the classes of the English language teachers while they were teaching the story. The technique applied by them was analyzed and interpreted using simple statistical tool of percentage.

a) Pre-Reading Activities/Techniques

By the name it is clear that it is the first stage of teaching the story in the class.

Here, the Table 1 deals with how teachers make the students prepare for the lesson and the task to be performed. Different activities performed by the teachers were evaluated in terms of four categories i.e. excellent, good, average and poor. After the teacher's warm up if all the students were motivated to read then the researcher ticked to the rank of excellent similarly, when most of the students got ready to read the short stories then ticked in the rank of good, and when half of the students got ready to read the stories then ticked in the rank of average but in the condition when the students did not show any interest to read the short stories then the researcher ranked in poor. In this way, the researcher had put these 4 categories to all the given activities.

Table 1. Pre-Reading Activities/Techniques Used by Teachers

Sr. No.	Activities/Techniques	Existing Condition			
		Excellent	Good	Average	Poor
1.	Motivation	33.3%	66.7%		
2.	Giving some general background	60%	26.7%	13.3%	
3.	Describing	80%	20%		
4.	Asking for guessing answer	76.7%	23.3%		
5.	Asking for guessing subject-matter	26.7%	73.3%		
6.	Teaching vocabulary of the story	90%	10%		

Table 1 showed that 33.3% English teachers of class ten motivated their students excellently and in 66.7% classes, they motivated in a good way but the researcher did not find any classes motivating their students in average and poor way. Similarly, regarding the general background, he found in 60% classes, teachers gave general background of the story to their students in an excellent way, in 26.7% classes, teachers gave general background of the story to their students in a good way and in 13.3% classes of them gave the general background to their students in average way. But the researcher did not find any teachers poor condition in providing general background of the story. The teachers (who gave general background in an excellent way) tried to elicit background from the student side as well through group discussion and on the basis of the responses made by the students, they elaborated the background. Majority of the teachers, in 80% classes, described the story in an excellent way.

The researcher found that in 20% classes, teachers described the story in a good way. In an excellent way described the events deeply with paying attention to the students' response. For excellent making students to guess the answer in 76.7% teachers tried to do so in an excellent way and in 23.3% classes they did so in good way. The teachers (who did so in an excellent way) asked the students to guess the answers, responded the students in an appropriate way. Students guessed the answers differently and teachers could get all of his student's response properly. But none of the classes was found in average and poor condition for this activity. As far as the subject matter is concerned, in 26.7% classes, teachers asked the students to guess in an excellent way. The teachers (who did so excellently) let their students guess what they would expect of the story from its title, they asked their students to predict what the story was about by letting them to read one or two paragraphs silently in the class. He found that in 73.3% classes they asked their students to guess what the story was about in a good way. But none of the classes were found in an average and poor condition regarding this activity. Regarding the pre-teaching of the vocabulary, the researcher found that in 90% classes, the teachers taught difficult vocabularies in an excellent way and in 10% classes, they taught the difficult vocabularies in a good way before teaching the story. But none of the teachers was found in average and poor condition regarding this activity.

Hence, it was found that the activities/techniques at pre-reading stage were satisfactory. Teachers made their students engage in different activities /techniques instead of doing all the things themselves.

b) While-Reading Activities/Techniques

Table 2 deals with the activities adopted by the teacher while teaching the story. Table 2 also deals with how the teachers presented the task to be performed, how they watched and evaluated their students' activities. As in the pre-reading activity, the same categories had also been used in the same way to evaluate the activities/techniques of teaching the story.

Table 2. While Reading Activities/Techniques Used by Teachers

Sr. No.	Activities/Techniques	Existing Condition			
		Excellent	Good	Average	Poor
1.	Helping students to understand the plot	6.7%	63.3%	30%	
2.	Helping students to understand the character	23.3%	60%	16.7%	
3.	Helping students to understand the setting	20%	53.3%	26.7%	
4.	Helping students to understand the style	16.7%	75.3%	8%	
5.	Helping students to understand the theme	90%	10%		
6.	Helping students to understand vocabulary	80%	20%		
7.	Translating into Nepali language	43%	33.7%	13.3%	10%
8.	Giving the summary of the story	30%	70%		

Table 2 shows that in 6.7% classes, the teachers helped their students to understand the plot of the story excellently. The researcher also found that who excellently did it firstly; the teachers briefly introduced what the plot was and described the series of events given in the story

with more examples and explanation. Similarly, he found the teachers (in 63.3% classes) helping their students to understand the plot in a good way. Those who did so did not introduce what the plot was to their students but they just described the events of the story with simple and clear language. It was also found that in 30% classes, teachers helped their students to understand the plot in an average way. Those who taught it averagely did not familiarize their students with what the plot was and also did not teach it with explanation. They just helped the students to understand the gist by giving lecture on the series of events in the story.

Similarly, the researcher found that in 23.3% classes, teachers helped their students to understand the character in excellent way, in 60% classes, teachers helped their students to understand the character in a good way and in 16.7% classes they taught it in an average way. The teachers (who did it in excellently way) firstly introduced briefly what was the role played by the character and described it with many illustrations. Whereas, the teachers (who did it in a good way) firstly asked what the character was.

Likewise, they taught about the character by comparing and making contrast with other people. And in 16.7% classes the teachers were found teaching the character in an average way. They just told the role of the character to the students.

Likewise, the researcher found that in 20% classes the teachers helped their students to understand the setting in an excellent way. Whereas, in 53.3% classes, the teachers helped their students to understand the setting in a good way and in 26.7% classes, the teachers helped the students to understand the setting in an average way.

Those who taught them in excellent way taught what the setting was and described the setting of the story with examples and encouraged students to explain about the setting of the given story. Those teachers who did it in a good way taught when and where story took place with examples and who did it in an average way just said about the setting. But none of the teachers found in poor condition for this activity.

Similarly, the researcher found that in 16.7% classes, teachers helped their students to understand the style in an excellent way, in 76.7% classes; teachers helped their students to understand the style in a good way and in 6.7% classes of them taught in an average way. But none of the teachers found in poor condition for this activity. However, he found that (in 90% classes) teachers helped their students to understand the gist in an excellent way and in 10% classes of them taught in a good way. But none of the teachers found in average and poor condition for this activity. Regarding the difficult vocabulary, in 100% classes, teachers were found that they taught difficult vocabularies to their students in an excellent way. Those who taught them in an excellent way taught the words with their contextual meaning. They encouraged their students a lot to get the meaning from the context first and if they were wrong, teachers told the meaning with context.

In translating a story in Nepal, the researcher found that in 56.7% classes, teachers did it excellently and used the translation judiciously. They translated only those terms which the students were feeling difficulties with in 20% classes, teachers were found that they used the translation in a good way, in 13.3% classes, teachers did it in an average way and in 10% classes, teachers were found that they used the translation in a poor way; they translated the whole story into Nepali. Majority of the teachers, i.e., in 66.7 % classes of the teachers emphasized on language and grammatical aspects of the story in an excellent way whereas in 33.3% classes of teachers emphasized the language and grammatical aspect of the story in a good way while teaching it into the class. But none of the teachers were found in average and poor condition for this activity.

Regarding the summary, the researcher found that in 86.7% classes, teachers summarized the story in brief at the end of the lesson whereas, in 13.3% classes of them summarized in an elaborative way. They often used mother tongue in summarizing the story. Similarly, the researcher found that in 30% classes, teachers used the communicative technique excellently and in 70% classes of them used it in a good way. Those teachers who did it excellently provided the majority of the class time for interaction to the students and encouraged them to take part in interaction one by one. Those teachers who did it in a good way engaged the students in group interaction. But none of the classes were found in an average and poor condition for this activity. In 6.7 % classes, teachers used narration techniques excellently.

c) Post –Reading Activities/Techniques

Here, the teachers clarify the ambiguities if the students are confused. Students' answers are checked by the teachers. The following table shows what and how the teachers clarified of the students:

Table 3. Post-Reading Activities/Techniques Used by Teachers

Sr. No.	Activities/Techniques	Existing Condition			
		Excellent	Good	Average	Poor
1.	Interpretation of the main theme of the story	73.3%	20%	6.7%	
2.	To help students to understand narrative point of view	10%	40%	33.3%	16.7%
3.	Writing Activities	60%	40%		
4.	Discussion	100%			

By the above table it is clear that in 73.3% classes, teachers interpreted the main theme of the story excellently. Those teachers who did it excellently first introduced what the theme was to their students and encouraged them to take part in interaction. Teachers i.e., in 20% classes interpreted the main theme of the story in a good way. Though they did not introduce what the theme was to their students, they taught the theme to their students with frequent interaction. Whereas the researcher found that in 6.7% classes of the teachers interpreted the main theme of the story in an average way. They themselves gave the central idea of the story to their students. It was found that in 10% classes, teachers helped the students to understand the narrative point of view excellently, in 40% classes; teachers helped the students to understand the narrative point of view in a good way and asked them to interpret the story using their own language. Classes i.e., in 33.3% classes of them helped them to understand the narrative point of view in average way and in 16.7% classes; teachers helped the students to understand the narrative point of view poorly. As far as written activities are concerned, the researcher found in 60% classes, teachers involved their students in different kinds of written activities whereas in 40% classes of them were found that they let their students write the review of the story.

Similarly, the researcher found in 100% classes, teachers did the critical discussion about the story involving the students in it. And they let their students engaged in discussion to the given questions. Here, what the researcher found was the post- reading activities /techniques of the teachers were good.

From the extensive analysis and interpretation of data and drawn of the result, it is concluded that there is no specific way of teaching English stories Teacher can select and design any methods to be suited to address the level of learners and nature of the courses as well as the teaching context. Blending of different methods or mixing different methods, makes classroom effective and meaningful. Wise selecting and mixing of different methods inside the classroom are useful to motivate the students and create interest and curiosity to study stories. It also helps to boost up the learning outcome of students. To develop competency in the side of the learners and to get expected outcome it is

better to design our own methods addressing the needs of classroom rather following the traditional ways of teaching stories. Practice and selection of different methods makes classroom lively. It also reduces monotony of students while learning second language and grammar.

4.2 Findings

From the analysis of raw data, the researcher came to the ultimate conclusion that it has been found that most of the time in classes i.e. 70% time classes, teachers spend the time in lecturing and 30% time they involved the students in activities.

Similarly, it has been found that 33% classes were motivated excellently, whereas 66.7% were in good way. Likewise, it has found that 60% classes were given general background about the story in excellently; whereas 26% in good way and 13.3% in average. Likewise, in 90% classes, vocabularies were taught in good way. In the same way, 23.3% classes, teachers helped their students to understand the character in excellent way, 60% helped in good way and 16.7% in an average way. Similarly, the researcher found in 16.7% classes students were helped to understand the style in an excellent way, 76.7% were found helped in a good way and 6.7% in an average way.

Likewise, in 62.3% class techniques were used in good way and in 30% classes, they were used in an average way, in 6.7% classes, they were used in excellent way. Similarly, in 73.3% class interpretation of the main theme of the story was done in excellent way, in 20% classes in good way and in 6.7% classes, it was done in average way.

In the someway, in 60% classes, students were guided in writing activities in excellent way and in 40% classes they were support in good way.

5. Conclusion

From the above of analysis and interpretation of the data following conclusions are drawn:

- It was found that the activities at pre- reading stage were satisfactory. Teachers made their students engage in different activities /techniques i.e., guessing about the story; brainstorming about the questions related to the story, etc. instead of doing all the things themselves.
- The researcher found that the techniques presented by the teachers at while- reading stage were good. In this stage, teachers made their students active in doing all the activities like predicting about the story by reading the first paragraph rather than doing all the things themselves.
- It was found that the activities presented by the teachers at post- reading stage were also good. In this stage, teachers mad their students active in doing all the activities like asking to summarize the story, to develop similar story, etc. rather than doing all the things themselves.
- The researcher found that among the above mentioned three techniques the while- reading activities/techniques were practiced most.

References

- Abrams, M. H. (2001). *A glossary of literary terms*. Harcourt, New Delhi: India Private Limited.
- Collie, J., & Slater, S. (1987). *Literature in the language classroom: A resource book of ideas and activities*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Joshi, J. (2008). *Teaching English short stories interactively* (Unpublished M.Ed. thesis). Tribhuvan University, Kirtipur, Nepal.
- Kshetri, J. B. (2010). *Activities in teaching short stories* (Unpublished M.Ed. thesis). Tribhuvan University, Kirtipur, Nepal.
- Lazar, G. (1993). *Literature and language teaching: A guide for teachers and trainers*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- McWilliams, B. (1995). *The art of telling stories*. Retrieved September 1, 2020 from <http://www.eldrbarry.net>.
- Nunan, D. (1992). *Research methods in language learning*. New York: Cambridge University Press.
- Regmi, S. (2011). *Activities used in teaching literature* (Unpublished M.Ed. thesis). Tribhuvan University, Kirtipur, Nepal.